

Exploration of Mathematical Minds as Emotional Factors in Design

Focused on cross-cultural cognitive diversity by mathematical minds

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Abstract: In the development of human products, the knowledge of cultural inclination in human perception should be utilized effectively in terms of considering a user's way of thinking in design. We studied two different ways of recognizing images by culture: attribute-oriented thoughts and relationship-oriented thoughts. According to our precedent experiment (2009), despite regional similarities, Japanese's attribute-oriented thoughts were different from the results of Koreans. As other factors that create the cognitive differences between Japanese and Koreans, in this study, we examined their mathematical skills and interests. From the result, we found that the attribute-oriented thought of Japanese males can vary with mathematical skills and interests, and that Korean subjects' attribute-oriented thought may not be associated with mathematical minds as much as the Japanese subjects. Additionally in cross-cultural comparison, we found the remarkable differences in attribute-oriented thought between Japanese male subjects who have high-leveled mathematical skills and Korean male subjects who have high or low-leveled mathematical skills, and also between Japanese male subjects who like mathematics and Korean male subjects who like or dislike mathematics. From this cognitive diversity, we learned that Japanese male university students have a cultural nature which has a strong cognitive diversity by mathematical skills and interests.

Key words: *Recognition Processes, Mathematical Skills and Interests, Attribute-Oriented Thoughts*

1. Introduction

In recent years, many researchers of fields such as product marketing and user-interface design are focusing their attention on the consumer's emotions. We are at the stage for another leap forward in the development of new understanding and vision of emotional factors in Design through innovative exploration. We focused our attention on their recognition processes as a method to perceive the consumer's emotional factors. Recognition processes have been studied in the fields of humanities, social sciences, cognitive sciences, and psychology as well as marketing, education, and interface design which need knowledge of specific groups' ways of thinking. In our precedent experiment (2009), we examined if we could observe the divergences in recognition processes among different cultures. As a result, it was found that Japanese and European subjects (British and Dutch) had stronger tendencies in attribute-oriented thought than Korean subjects. Despite regional similarities, the

Japanese's recognition processes were much different from the results of the Koreans. Because we have witnessed other factors that create the cognitive differences between Japanese and Koreans, in this study, we focused our attention on their mathematical skills and interests to support the notion. We explored if we could observe the divergences in recognition processes between Japanese and Korean by their mathematical minds.

2. Precedent Studies about Recognition Processes

Although there have been limited researches on cultural differences in recognition processes, there is data indicating that cultural differences do exist. For example, Chiu (1972) examined such divergences in categorization between Chinese and American children, using pictures of artifacts, plants, and animals. A 28-item cognitive style test was constructed to serve as a measuring material. It contained 21 items adapted from the Sigel Cognitive Style Test (Sigel, 1967) and 7 items from the study by Kagan et al. (1963) [1]. On each trial in Chiu's study, the participants were presented with three pictures (e.g., a cow, a chicken, and grass), and were asked to group the two pictures they thought best belonged together. The participants were also asked to explain their choices (e.g., "Because they are both animals"). The participants' responses were classified as descriptive-analytic (identifying similar parts of stimuli and differentiating based on those similarities: e.g., "Because they are both holding a gun"), descriptive-whole (identifying whether a stimulus as a whole is similar to another whole stimulus: e.g., "Because they are both large"), inferential-categorical (categorizing based on inferences made about the stimuli that are grouped together; e.g., "Because they both have a motor"), and relational-contextual (categorizing based on functional and thematic relationships: e.g., "Because a mother takes care of a baby"). The reactions showed that the American children were most likely to respond using descriptive - analytic, descriptive - whole, and inferential - categorical categorizations than the Chinese children; that the Chinese children were superior to respond using relational -contextual categorizations than the American children [2]. Considered together, Chiu's results suggest that Chinese children are apt to greatly categorize the stimuli by identifying relationships, whereas American children have a greater tendency to categorize them through recognizing similarities.

After 30 years, Sara J. Unsworth, Christopher R. Sears and Penny M. Pexman (2005) examined some similar experiments. In their researches, Chinese and Western participants were asked to look at sets of three pictures (e.g., a tire, a car, and a bus), and to decide which two pictures of each set best belonged together. The Chinese participants were equally likely to group items together if they shared a relationship (e.g., tire-car) and if they shared a category (e.g., bus-car), whereas the Western participants were more likely to group items together if they belonged to the same category [3]. These results are similar to Chiu's study; American children are more likely to classify items together if they are more similar to each other, and that Chinese children are more likely to classify items if they share a relationship. In our recent study (2009), we compared the differences in recognition processes among Japanese, Korean, Dutch, and British university students. On each trial, the participants were asked to look at sets of three pictures (e.g., a pencil, a brush, and a notepad), and were asked to group the two pictures they thought best belonged together (a pencil-a brush, or a pencil-a notepad). The reactions showed that the European subjects had greater tendencies in attribute-oriented thought than the Korean subjects. This inclination was similar to the results of precedent studies (Chiu and Sara et al.) related to the regional comparison (the East vs. the West). However, in spite of their regional similarities, the Japanese subjects

had greater tendencies in attribute-oriented thought than the Korean subjects [4]. Accordingly, we thought that there exist the other factors that create cognitive differences.

3. Exploration of Mathematical Minds as Factors that create Recognition Processes

3.1. Goal and Methods

In the case of our 2009 study, we invited design major students as the participants in experiment. Through the consideration of educational background, we found there were some differences of mathematical educational background among nationality; as for the Dutch and British subjects, there were many graduate students and most of undergraduate majors were in the field of engineering; as for the Japanese subjects, they learned a lot of knowledge related to statistics and engineering through the lectures in their majors; on the other hand, the Korean subjects were undergraduate students and they didn't need high-levelled mathematical skills in their classes. Both engineering and statistics need analytical thought and Mathematical skills. Therefore, there was a possibility that the mathematical skills of the European and Japanese subjects are higher than the Korean subjects. In addition, the following is a definition of 'mathematics' in a dictionary; the science of numbers and shapes. Branches of mathematics include Arithmetic, Algebra, Geometry and Trigonometry. Geometry is a branch of mathematics that deals with the measurements and relationships of line, angle, surface and solids in particular object or shape, and Arithmetic is a type of mathematics that deals with the adding, multiplying, etc. of numbers [5]. We estimated that mathematical skill including Arithmetic and Geometric thought would be associated with attribute-oriented thoughts which identify Arithmetic and Geometric similarities (e.g., numbers, shape, or structure) among stimuli in our experiment. Therefore, there is a possibility that the AT of the European and Japanese subjects are stronger than Korean subjects.

Additionally, we assumed "Mathematical Interest (MI)" as one of the factors which creates cognitive differences. AT is based on the analytical thought in a sense of having a cognitive tendency that categorizes objects through analyzing similarities in attributes. We estimated that persons who liked mathematics would be apt to think analytically, and also they would be apt to have the AT. The judgment for mathematical interests set the standard in 'self valuation'. Meanwhile, as for MS and MI, we estimated that participants would use the mental activity of 'Intelligence' related to mathematics when they were taking an examination of mathematics, and use the mental activity of 'Interest' about mathematics when they are thinking the liking of mathematics. A term of 'Mind' includes mental activity like 'Intelligence' and 'Interest' [6]. Therefore we used "Mathematical Minds (MM)" as a term including the mental activities related to MS and MI. In a pretest (Park & Yamanaka 2010), we found a possibility that mathematical minds can influence on cognitive tendency of Japanese male subjects [7]. In this study, our goal was to compare the cognitive differences according to mathematical minds between Japanese and Korean university students.

As a method of experiment, we presented three images per question; 'Target', 'Object A' (which is similar to 'target' in attributes: shape, function, structure and category) and 'Object B' (which is familiar with 'target' in mutual relations). We showed one target picture (e.g., a pencil) and two related pictures (e.g., a brush, and a note pad) to the subjects and asked them to pair the target picture with the related picture that they felt belonged best together: a pencil-a brush or a pencil-a note pad. We categorized pairing 'a pencil' (target) with 'a brush' (object

A) as a attribute-oriented thought (AT), and pairing ‘a pencil’ (Target) with ‘a note pad’ (Object B) as a relationship - oriented thought (RT) (Table 1). We prepared six sets of images (Figure 1). On each trial, the images were presented to the participants with the question of ‘between A and B, which one is the closest to the target?’

Table 1: The measuring method for cognitive style

Two objects related to ‘Target’	‘Object A’ ; which is similar to ‘target’ in attributes: shape, function, structure, category	‘Object B’ ; which is familiar with ‘target’ in mutual relations
Recognition Processes	(Attribute-oriented Thought) AT	(Relationship -oriented Thought) RT
Categorization (an example)	Target - ‘Object A’ (a pencil - a brush)	Target - ‘Object B’ (a pencil - a note pad)

Q.	Target	A	B
1			
	Target-A: similar shape and similar kinds (machines), Target-B: contextual relationship (operate a mouse)		
2			
	Target-A: similar structure and similar kinds (parts of body), Target-B: contextual relationship (wear shoes)		
3			
	Target-A: similar shape and similar kinds (tools for drawing), Target-B: contextual relationship (write on a note)		
4			
	Target-A: similar structure and similar kinds (faces), Target-B: contextual relationship (see a hand mirror)		
5			
	Target-A: similar shape and similar kinds (containers), Target-B: contextual relationship (drink coffee)		
6			
	Target-A: similar shape and similar kinds (animals), Target-B: causation (cheese is made from milk)		

Figure 1: Stimuli [4]

In terms of mathematical minds of the participants, the two points of view were considered. One is a mathematical skill and the other is a personal mathematical interest. As for *Mathematical Skills (MS)*, we needed

an objective judgment of the participant’s ability for mathematics. For that reason, we looked for a method that helps to evaluate mathematical skills of participants objectively; e.g., the majors related to mathematics in universities require high-leveled MS. Students who are applying for admission, they have to pass the high-leveled mathematics examination presented by the department of mathematics-based major [8]. Therefore, as a standard measuring for the level of MS, we assumed whoever a person who selected high-leveled mathematical test had an ability of high-leveled MS. Therefore we considered two groups as a standard for comparing participant’s MS; a group of persons who take high-leveled mathematical test for those who had an ability of high-leveled MS, and a group of persons who did not take high-leveled mathematical test for those who had an ability of low-leveled MS. To estimate the level of MI, we asked the following question to the participants; “do you like mathematics?”, and then they were told to select an answer from “yes”, “neutral” and “No”. It is difficult to examine the tendencies of all people in culture. In this case, researchers usually estimate the tendency of a whole group by referring to the tendency of a part of the group. In this study, 62 Japanese and 57 Korean university students were participated. We researched their majors as mathematic-based majors group vs. non-mathematic-based majors group and asked their mathematical interest (Table 2).

Table 2: Participant’s major and mathematical interest

Nationality	Japanese students (Tsukuba University)			
Major	Mathematics-based		Non-mathematics-based	
		Environmental Systems, Computer Science, Medicine, International Relations, Earth Science, Engineering System, Psychology, Applied Science and Technology, Information Science, Law Psychology, Physics, Biology, Knowledge Information - library Science,		Sports, Applied Linguistics, Japanese Classic, Japanese History, Japanese Culture, Comparison Culture, Cultural Anthropology, Creature-Resources, Nursing, Sociology, Art, English Studies
Numbers of people	Female	Male	Female	Male
	10	22	24	6
Like	5	14	9	3
Dislike	5	4	6	2
Neutral	0	4	9	1
Sum	32		30	
	62			

Nationality	Korean students (Seoul national university)			
Major	Mathematics-based		Non-mathematics-based	
		Atmosphere science, Biomaterials engineering, Chemical bionics, Chemistry, City engineering, Civil engineering, Computer engineering, Construction environmental engineering, global environment, industrial engineering, Life science, Machine aeronautical engineering		humanities, Chinese, design, English education, Geography education, history, industrial design, Korean traditional music, Management, oriental history, Politics, social education, social science, sociology, spatial design, visual communication design
Numbers of people	Female	Male	Female	Male
	10	17	20	10
Like	6	10	5	6
Dislike	1	3	8	2
Neutral	3	4	7	2
Sum	27		30	
	57			

3.2 Japanese’s cognitive inclinations by mathematical minds

3.2.1. Analysis

The tendencies of attribute-oriented thoughts (Selection ratio of object ‘A’) between 32 *mathematic-based majors* and 30 *non-mathematic-based majors* were analyzed. In the results of the *Chi-square Test*, there were no significant differences between two groups in all questions. Additionally, we compared both genders to observe whether any differences would be found. As a result, there were no significant differences in all questions among females, but there were significant differences in question 2 ($\chi^2 = 9.282$) and 5 ($\chi^2 = 6.212$) among males (Table 3).

Table 3: Comparison of attribute-oriented thoughts by Japanese subjects’ mathematical skills

Q.	Selection ratio (%) of object ‘A’(Object which is similar to ‘target’ in attributes)			χ^2 test
	<i>32 Mathematics-based majors</i>	<i>30 Non-mathematics-based majors</i>	Average	P value
1	56.25	66.67	61.29	0.4001
2	84.38	73.33	79.03	0.2858
3	59.38	46.67	53.23	0.3162
4	65.63	43.33	54.84	0.0780
5	75.00	60.00	67.74	0.2067
6	81.25	76.67	79.03	0.6577
Q.	<i>Mathematics-based majors (10 females)</i>	<i>Non-mathematics-based majors (24 females)</i>	Average	P value
1	70.00	62.50	64.71	0.6767
2	70.00	83.33	79.41	0.3810
3	50.00	50.00	50.00	1.0000
4	50.00	45.83	47.06	0.8245
5	80.00	70.83	73.53	0.5809
6	90.00	83.33	85.29	0.6170
Q.	<i>Mathematics-based majors (22 males)</i>	<i>Non-mathematics-based majors (6 males)</i>	Average	P value
1	50.00	83.33	57.14	0.1436
2	90.91	33.33	78.57	0.0023*
3	63.64	33.33	57.14	0.1837
4	72.73	33.33	64.29	0.0742
5	72.73	16.67	60.71	0.0127*
6	77.27	50.00	71.43	0.1899

Next, the tendencies of attribute-oriented thoughts (Selection ratio of object ‘A’) between 31 *students who like mathematics* and 17 *students who dislike mathematics* were analyzed. As shown in the result of the *Chi-square (χ^2) Test*, students who like mathematics had stronger tendencies towards attribute-oriented thoughts than students who dislike mathematics in question 3 ($\chi^2 = 4.697$), and 4 ($\chi^2 = 6.947$). Additionally, we compared both genders to observe whether any differences would be found. As a result, there were no differences in all questions among females, but there were significant differences in question 2 ($\chi^2 = 6.933$), 3 ($\chi^2 = 5.247$), 4 ($\chi^2 = 5.033$) and 5 ($\chi^2 = 6.933$) among males (table 4).

Table 4: Comparison of attribute-oriented thought by Japanese’s mathematical interests

Q.	Selection ratio (%) of object ‘A’(Object which is similar to ‘target’ in attributes)			χ^2 test
	<i>31 people who like Mathematics</i>	<i>17 people who dislike Mathematics</i>	Average	P value
1	61.29	58.82	60.42	0.8673
2	83.87	64.71	77.08	0.1308
3	67.74	35.29	56.25	0.0302*
4	74.19	35.29	60.42	0.0084*
5	80.65	64.71	75.00	0.2226
6	87.10	70.59	81.63	0.3287

Q.	14 females who like Mathematics	11 females who dislike Mathematics	Average	P value
1	64.29	63.64	64.00	0.9732
2	78.57	81.82	80.00	0.8403
3	64.29	45.45	56.00	0.3464
4	64.29	36.36	52.00	0.1654
5	81.82	71.43	76.00	0.5460
6	85.71	81.82	84.00	0.7920
Q.	17 males who like Mathematics	6 males who dislike Mathematics	Average	P value
1	58.82	50.00	56.52	0.7078
2	88.24	33.33	73.91	0.0085*
3	70.59	16.67	56.52	0.0220*
4	82.35	33.33	69.57	0.0249*
5	88.24	33.33	73.91	0.0085*
6	88.24	50.00	78.26	0.0509

3.2.2. Results and Findings

There were no significant differences of attribute-oriented thoughts by majors (mathematics-based majors vs. non-mathematics-based majors) in all six questions (Refer table 3); these results indicate that there were no cognitive differences by mathematical skills (high-leveled vs. low-leveled). This result differed with our assumption. However, some considerable differences of attribute-oriented thoughts by mathematical interest (like vs. dislike) were shown in question 3 and 4. Especially there were significant differences in question 2, 3, 4 and 5 among males (Refer table 4). These results correspond with our assumption to some degree. Next, we considered attribute-oriented thoughts by mathematical skills and interests in relation to gender. As a result, we found similar inclinations between mathematical skills and interests; there were no significant differences among females in all questions, but there were significant differences among males: in mathematical skills (Q. 2 and 5): in mathematical interests (Q. 2, 3, 4 and 5). This result confirmed that the effect of mathematical skills and interests towards attribute-oriented thoughts were more noticeable for males than females (Refer table 3 and 4).

3.2.3. Conclusions

We examined the influence of mathematical minds (skills and interests) as the factors on attribute-oriented thoughts. 62 Japanese university students participated in this experiment. There were significant differences between mathematic-based male majors and non-mathematic-based male majors towards attribute-oriented thought. Also, certain considerable differences with attribute-oriented thought by mathematical interest (like vs. dislike) were viewed among males. Finally, we found a possibility that Japanese male subjects, attribute-oriented thought may be associated with emotion on mathematical interest as well as mathematical skills.

3.3. Korean's cognitive inclinations by mathematical minds

3.3.1. Analysis

The tendencies of attribute-oriented thoughts (Selection ratio of object 'A') between 27 *mathematic-based majors* and 30 *non-mathematic-based majors* were analyzed. In the results of the *Chi-square Test*, there were no significant differences between two groups in all questions except question 3 ($\chi^2 = 4.967$). Additionally, we compared both genders to observe whether any differences would be found. As a result, there were no significant

differences in all questions among females, but there were significant differences in question 3 ($\chi^2 = 3.844$) among males (table 5). Next, the tendencies of attribute-oriented thoughts (Selection ratio of object 'A') between 27 students who like mathematics and 14 students who dislike mathematics were analyzed. As shown in the result of the Chi-square (χ^2) Test, there were no significant differences between two groups in all questions. Additionally, we compared both genders to observe whether any differences would be found. As a result, there were no differences in all questions among females, but there were significant differences in question 2 ($\chi^2 = 4.038$) among males (table 6).

Table 5: Comparison of attribute-oriented thoughts by Korean subjects' mathematical skills

Q.	Selection ratio (%) of object 'A' (Object which is similar to 'target' in attributes)			χ^2 test
	27 Mathematics-based majors	30 Non-mathematics-based majors	Average	P value
1	11.11	10.00	10.53	0.8914
2	59.26	50.00	54.39	0.4834
3	51.85	23.33	36.84	0.0258*
4	29.63	26.67	28.07	0.8037
5	66.67	60.00	63.16	0.6024
6	66.67	60.00	63.16	0.6024
Q.	Mathematics-based majors (10 females)	Non-mathematics-based majors (20 females)	Average	P value
1	0.00	15.00	10.00	0.1967
2	70.00	65.00	66.67	0.7842
3	40.00	25.00	30.00	0.3980
4	40.00	30.00	33.33	0.5839
5	60.00	55.00	56.67	0.7945
6	50.00	70.00	63.33	0.2839
Q.	Mathematics-based majors (17 males)	Non-mathematics-based majors (10 males)	Average	P value
1	17.65	0.00	11.11	0.1588
2	52.94	20.00	40.74	0.0925
3	58.82	20.00	44.44	0.0499*
4	23.53	20.00	22.22	0.8313
5	70.59	70.00	70.37	0.9742
6	76.47	40.00	62.96	0.0581

Table 6: Comparison of attribute-oriented thoughts by Korean's mathematical interests

Q.	Selection ratio (%) of object 'A' (Object which is similar to 'target' in attributes)			χ^2 test
	27 people who like Mathematics	14 people who dislike Mathematics	Average	P value
1	14.81	7.14	12.20	0.4765
2	55.56	50.00	53.66	0.7352
3	44.44	21.43	36.59	0.1468
4	25.93	14.29	21.95	0.3932
5	66.67	50.00	60.98	0.2995
6	62.96	64.29	63.41	0.9335
Q.	11 females who like Mathematics	9 females who dislike Mathematics	Average	P value
1	9.09	11.11	10.00	0.8809
2	63.64	77.78	70.00	0.4924
3	36.36	22.22	30.00	0.4924
4	27.27	22.22	25.00	0.7952
5	63.64	44.44	55.00	0.3907
6	54.55	77.78	65.00	0.2785

Q.	16 males who like Mathematics	5 males who dislike Mathematics	Average	P value
1	18.75	0.00	14.29	0.2956
2	50.00	0.00	38.10	0.0445*
3	50.00	20.00	42.86	0.2367
4	25.00	0.00	19.05	0.2140
5	68.75	60.00	66.67	0.7171
6	68.75	40.00	61.90	0.2479

3.3.2. Conclusions

We examined the influence of mathematical minds (skills and interests) as the factors on attribute-oriented thoughts. 57 Korean university students participated in this experiment. There were no significant differences between 27 mathematic-based majors and 30 non-mathematic-based majors towards attribute-oriented thoughts in all six questions except one. And there were no considerable differences of attribute-oriented thoughts by mathematical interests (like vs. dislike) in all six questions. Finally, we found a possibility that Korean attribute-oriented thoughts may not be associated with mathematical minds.

4. Discussion

4.1. Japan-Korea comparison of cognitive inclinations

As a first discussion, we explored if we could find cross-cultural cognitive diversity. For that, we analyzed items of question that show significant cognitive differences between Japanese and Korean students.

Table 7: Comparisons of attribute-oriented thought between Japanese and Korean subjects

Q.	Selection ratio (%) of object 'A'(Object which is similar to 'target' in attributes)			χ^2 test
	62 Japanese	57 Korean	Average	P value
1	61.29	12.28	37.82	<.0001*
2	79.03	54.39	67.23	0.0042*
3	53.23	36.84	45.38	0.0729
4	54.84	28.07	42.02	0.0031*
5	67.74	63.16	65.55	0.5991
6	79.03	63.16	71.43	0.0555
Q.	34 Japanese females	30 Korean females	Average	P value
1	64.71	10.00	39.06	<.0001*
2	79.41	66.67	73.44	0.2493
3	50.00	30.00	40.63	0.1040
4	47.06	33.33	40.63	0.2646
5	73.53	56.67	65.63	0.1564
6	85.29	63.33	75.00	0.0429*
Q.	28 Japanese males	27 Korean males	Average	P value
1	57.14	14.81	36.36	0.0011*
2	78.57	40.74	60.00	0.0042*
3	57.14	44.44	50.91	0.3463
4	64.29	22.22	43.64	0.0017*
5	60.71	70.37	65.45	0.4515
6	71.43	62.96	67.27	0.5036

We compared selection ratio (%) of object 'A' (attribute-oriented thoughts) between Japanese and Korean subjects (table 7). As the result, there were significant differences in three questions (1, 2 and 4). Next, we considered the recognition tendencies between two nationalities in relation to gender. In the result, we found that there were two types of questions that showed similar inclination between females and males; no significant

differences in both genders (Q. 3 and 5); notable differences in the subjects (Q. 1). On the other hand, there were significant differences among females in Q. 6 and among males in Q. 2 and 4.

4.2. Japan-Korea comparison of cognitive inclinations according to mathematical minds

As a second discussion, we explored if we could find cross-cultural cognitive diversity by mathematical minds. For that, we analyzed items of question that showed significant cognitive differences between Japanese and Korean students according to mathematical skills and interests (Table 8). Additionally, table 9 shows the cognitive diversity according to mathematical minds between Japanese and Korean subjects; we remade table 8 so that we can recognize the degree of cognitive differences more clearly by variables of mathematical minds.

Table 8: The items of question which showed significant cognitive diversity according to mathematical minds between 62 Japanese and 57 Korean university students

Cognitive diversity by mathematical skills			
Ratio of Attribute-oriented thoughts : Korean < Japanese		Japanese	
		High- leveled	Low- leveled
Korean	High- leveled	1, 2, 4	1 [e]
	Low- leveled	1, 2, 3, 4	1 [f]
: Korean female < Japanese female		Japanese female	
Korean female	High- leveled	1	1
	Low- leveled	1	1
: Korean male < Japanese male 5* = Korean > Japanese		Japanese male	
Korean male	High- leveled	2, 4 [a]	1, 5*
	Low- leveled	1, 2, 3, 4, 6 [b]	1, 5
Cognitive diversity by mathematical interests			
Ratio of Attribute-oriented thoughts : Korean < Japanese		Japanese	
		Like	Dislike
Korean	Like	1, 2, 4, 6	1 [g]
	Dislike	1, 2, 3, 4, 5	1 [h]
: Korean female < Japanese female		Japanese female	
Korean female	Like	1	1
	Dislike	1, 3, 4	1
: Korean male < Japanese male		Japanese male	
Korean male	Like	1, 2, 4 [c]	-
	Dislike	1, 2, 3, 4, 6 [d]	-

Through the analysis, we could learn that the degree of cognitive diversity between Japanese and Korean participants can be different by mathematical skills (high or low-leveled) and interests (liking or disliking); especially there was considerable cognitive diversity among Japanese male students who have high-leveled mathematical skills and Korean male students who have high or low-leveled mathematical skills (refer [a], and [b] in table 8 and 9); also among Japanese male students who like mathematics and Korean male students who like or dislike mathematics (refer [c], and [d] in table 8 and 9). On the other hand, there were no considerable cognitive diversity among Japanese students who have low-leveled mathematical skills and Korean students who

have high or low-leveled mathematical skills (refer [e], and [f] in table 8); also among Japanese students who dislike mathematics and Korean students who like or dislike mathematics (refer [g], and [h] in table 8 and 9). From these cognitive comparisons, we could cognize two possibilities; one is that Japanese male subjects have a cultural nature which has a strong attribute-oriented thought by high-leveled mathematical education; the other is that the cognitive differences between Japanese and Korean students were remarkable among male subjects.

Table 9: The cognitive diversity according to mathematical minds between Japanese and Korean subjects

Participants	<i>Items of question that show significant differences between Japanese and Korean students by variables of mathematical skills</i>			
	Between high-leveled Japanese and high-leveled Korean	Between high-leveled Japanese and low-leveled Korean	Between low-leveled Japanese and high-leveled Korean	Between low-leveled Japanese and Korean
Whole	1, 2, 4	1, 2, 3, 4	1[e]	1[f]
Female	1	1	1	1
Male	2, 4[a]	1, 2, 3, 4, 6[b]	1, 5*	1, 5
Participants	<i>Items of question that show significant differences between Japanese and Korean students by variables of mathematical interests</i>			
	Between Japanese who like mathematics and Korean who like mathematics	Between Japanese who like mathematics and Korean who dislike mathematics	Between Japanese who dislike mathematics and Korean who like mathematics	Between Japanese and Korean who dislike mathematics
Whole	1, 2, 4, 6	1, 2, 3, 4, 5	1[g]	1[h]
Female	1	1, 3, 4	1	1
Male	1, 2, 4[c]	1, 2, 3, 4, 6[d]	-	-

4.3. Mathematical minds as emotional factors in design

In recent years, many researchers of fields such as product marketing and user-interface design are focusing their attention on the consumer's emotions. For example, Sharon Ng and Michael J. H. (2008) studied about "field dependency and brand cognitive structure". Researchers argue that people who ignore contextual information (i.e., field independents) are more likely to generalize summary evaluations from personal experiences of one product to another. They focus more on brand level belief, connecting numerous products by a single brand to the same set of beliefs (e.g., connecting a number of different Sony products to the same "good quality" belief). On the other hand, people who pay greater attention to contextual information (i.e., field dependents) are more likely to focus on specific, episodic information derived from their experience with the brand. They focus more on product level beliefs and store different sets of beliefs for different products (e.g., storing separate "quality" beliefs for different Sony products). The result of study shows that field independents are more likely to abstract information from episodic experiences and connect the same brand level beliefs to varied products by brand. On the other hand, field dependents focus more on individuating information of each experience and are more likely to store product specific beliefs [9]. Next is a study example in the field of design; Dong, Y. & Lee, K. P. (2008) examined "A Cross-cultural comparative study of users' perceptions of a webpage." In this, they compared the thought patterns of Chinese, Korean and American participants when looking at a webpage. As a result, they found different viewing patterns among participants. The Chinese and Korean subjects showed more similarities to holistic thought patterns, while American subjects showed more similarities to analytic thought patterns [10].

Both “the field independent thoughts” and “analytic thoughts” are involved in “Attributed-oriented Thoughts”. And mathematical minds can affect “Attributed-oriented Thoughts”. Therefore, there is a possibility that field independents have stronger mathematical minds than field dependents, and that American participants have stronger tendency of mathematical minds than Chinese and Korean participants; participants’ mathematical minds may be crucial factors that create cognitive diversity in two studies. Therefore, we suggest it is necessary to distinct the participants’ profile by mathematical minds (skills and interests) in future study.

5. Acknowledgement

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6. Conclusions

In this study, we explored mathematical minds as factors that create consumer’s cultural emotions. As a method, we examined two different ways of recognizing images by culture: attribute-oriented thoughts and relationship-oriented thoughts. Moreover, we explored mathematical minds as factors that create the cognitive diversity. 62 Japanese and 57 Korean university students participated in our study.

As the results of experiment, our remarkable findings go as followed;

- Japanese male subjects’ attribute-oriented thoughts were different in their mathematical minds (skills and interests).
- A possibility that Korean subjects’ attribute-oriented thoughts may not be associated with mathematical minds.
- There were remarkable cognitive diversities between Japanese male subjects who have high-levelled mathematical skills and Korean male subjects who have high or low-levelled mathematical skills, and also between Japanese male subjects who like mathematics and Korean male subjects who like or dislike mathematics.

In conclusion, the differences of the recognition processes by mathematical minds can vary according to culture; especially Japanese male subjects’ mathematical minds strongly showed as a factor that create cognitive diversity. Additionally, in cross-cultural comparison, we concluded that Japanese male subjects have a cultural nature which has a strong cognitive diversity by mathematical skills and interests. To confirm cultural-cognitive inclinations by mathematical minds, further research with diverse cultures are needed. This research will be handled in depth in future studies.

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